

Coaching Capability of School Paper Advisers in Nueva Ecija: Basis for a Training and Development Plan

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the coaching capability of secondary school paper advisers (SPAs) in the Schools Division of Nueva Ecija as basis for a training and development plan. It described the respondents' profile, evaluated their coaching capability in terms of coaching attitude, professional qualities, communication skills, analytical skills, and technological knowledge, and examined whether capability differed across selected profile variables. A descriptive quantitative design was used. Data were gathered through a validated survey questionnaire administered through Google Forms to 255 secondary SPAs selected through purposive sampling. Frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and analysis of variance were used to analyze the data. Findings showed that the respondents were predominantly female, commonly held Teacher III positions, generally had graduate-level units, and were largely assigned to rural schools. Although most

had attended campus journalism-related training, a substantial proportion had not received formal training. Overall coaching capability was rated effective ($M = 3.56$). Professional qualities obtained the highest mean ($M = 3.74$), followed by coaching attitude ($M = 3.70$), communication skills ($M = 3.63$), analytical skills ($M = 3.51$), and technological knowledge ($M = 3.24$), which was rated fairly effective. Coaching capability did not differ significantly according to age, gender, educational attainment, years of teaching experience, academic rank, or school location. A significant difference was found according to relevant trainings attended ($p = .001$). The findings indicate that sustained, needs-based training should prioritize technological knowledge while reinforcing the advisers' established coaching strengths.

Keywords: *school paper advisers, campus journalism, coaching capability, journalism education, technological knowledge, training and development plan*

INTRODUCTION

Campus journalism is an important component of education because it develops functional literacy, critical thinking, civic awareness, and responsible participation among learners. School publications provide students with opportunities to examine issues, gather evidence, communicate ideas, and express informed perspectives. In the Philippine basic education context, campus journalism is supported by Republic Act No. 7079, or the Campus Journalism Act of 1991, which recognizes the role of student publications in strengthening freedom of expression and journalistic competence.

The school paper adviser has a central role in sustaining a school publication and preparing campus journalists. Advisers guide student writers in reporting, writing, editing, ethics, layout, design, and responsible communication while allowing learners to develop an authentic student voice. The Journalism Education Association emphasizes that journalism educators need competencies in reporting, writing, communication, leadership, press law and ethics, fiscal responsibility, and multimedia design and production. As journalism practice

continues to evolve, advisers are also expected to respond to digital publication, online verification, multimedia storytelling, and data-driven reporting (Donsbach, 2014; Hewett, 2016; Splendore et al., 2016).

The Schools Division of Nueva Ecija has continued to participate in regional and national schools press conferences. However, the division's campus journalism performance indicated a need to examine whether SPAs possess the competencies required to guide student writers effectively. The concern is particularly relevant because capability may be influenced by access to relevant training, professional experience, academic preparation, and the technological demands of contemporary journalism.

This study assessed the coaching capability of secondary SPAs in Nueva Ecija and determined whether capability differed across selected profile variables. The findings were used as basis for a training and development plan that addresses capability gaps while sustaining the strengths of advisers in coaching student journalists.

Literature Review

Campus Journalism and the Role of School Paper Advisers

Campus journalism supports the development of student voice, literacy, critical thinking, and social responsibility. Bumanghat (2017) described campus journalism as a means of developing learners into functional and productive citizens. The school paper adviser is therefore not merely an activity coordinator but a coach who helps learners gather information, write responsibly, and observe ethical standards.

Journalism education increasingly requires a combination of general and specialized knowledge. Donsbach (2014) argued that journalism has become a knowledge profession, while Mensing and Ryfe (2013) emphasized the need for journalism education to adjust to changing industry practices. Advisers who guide student publications must be able to support traditional writing and editing skills while also recognizing the expanded demands of digital journalism.

Coaching Capability and Professional Competence

Effective coaching involves professional commitment, communication, analytical judgment, ethical practice, and the ability to provide appropriate technical guidance. Teacher effectiveness literature suggests that professional competence is shaped by multiple factors, including training, teaching experience, and professional preparation. Pa-alisbo (2017) emphasized the relevance of twenty-first-century skills to teacher performance, while Fabelico and Afalla (2020) highlighted perseverance, self-efficacy, and professional commitment in teaching practice.

Training is particularly important because it provides structured opportunities to address specific weaknesses and reinforce existing strengths. Rao (2009) noted that well-designed training programs can improve teachers' knowledge, skills, and competence. In the context of campus journalism, training can strengthen both traditional coaching skills and emerging competencies in digital design, online research, multimedia production, and ethical social media use.

Technology and Contemporary Journalism Coaching

The digital environment has transformed how news is produced, distributed, and consumed. Journalism education now includes digital publishing, data journalism, multimedia production, and online research (Du & Thornburg, 2011; Hewett, 2016; Splendore et al., 2016). These developments require SPAs to guide students not only in writing and editing but also in the responsible use of technology for information gathering, verification, design, and dissemination.

Technological knowledge is therefore an essential dimension of coaching capability. Advisers who are competent in software applications, internet research, digital layout, online communication, and social media ethics are better positioned to prepare student journalists for contemporary publication practices.

METHODS

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive quantitative research design to assess the coaching capability of secondary SPAs in the Schools Division of Nueva Ecija and to determine whether capability differed according to selected profile variables.

Research Locale, Participants, and Sampling Technique

The study was conducted in the Schools Division of Nueva Ecija. The respondents were 255 secondary SPAs from participating junior and senior high schools. Purposive sampling was used because the respondents were selected on the basis of their assigned roles as advisers or coaches of school publications.

Research Instrument

Data were gathered using a survey questionnaire previously developed and content-validated by the researcher. The instrument consisted of three parts: respondent profile, coaching capability response, and personal experience response. Coaching capability was measured using a four-point Likert scale across five dimensions: coaching attitude, professional qualities, communication skills, analytical skills, and technological knowledge. Mean scores were interpreted as effective (3.25-4.00), fairly effective (2.50-3.24), less effective (1.75-2.49), or not effective (1.00-1.74).

Data Gathering Procedure and Ethical Consideration

Permission to conduct the study was secured from the education program supervisor in charge of campus journalism and the principals of participating schools. Respondents were informed of the purpose of the study before the questionnaire was distributed through Google Forms. Participation was voluntary, and anonymity and confidentiality were observed throughout data collection and reporting.

Data Analysis

Frequency and percentage were used to summarize the respondents' profile. Weighted mean was used to describe coaching capability. Analysis of variance was used to test differences in coaching capability according to age, gender, educational attainment, years of teaching experience, academic rank, relevant trainings attended, and school location. Statistical significance was evaluated at the .05 level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the School Paper Advisers

The respondent profile shows that the SPA group was predominantly female and commonly assigned to rural schools. The largest age group was 31-40 years old. Most respondents had earned units in a master's program, held Teacher III positions, and had attended relevant training. Nevertheless, nearly three in ten respondents had not attended campus journalism-related training, indicating that access to professional development remained uneven.

Table 1. *Selected Profile Highlights of the School Paper Advisers*

Profile Variable	Largest or Relevant Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	31-40 years old	85	33.33%
Gender	Female	210	82.35%
Educational attainment	Earned units in master's program	164	64.31%
Years in teaching service	1-10 years	139	54.51%
Academic rank	Teacher III	129	50.59%
Relevant trainings attended	With training	180	70.59%
School location	Rural	236	92.55%

Note. The table presents selected dominant or relevant profile categories to provide a concise journal-style summary of the respondent profile.

Level of Coaching Capability

The SPAs obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.56, which was interpreted as effective. Professional qualities ranked highest, followed by coaching attitude, communication skills, and analytical skills. Technological knowledge obtained the lowest mean and was the only dimension rated fairly effective. This pattern indicates that the advisers possessed strong professional and coaching foundations but required additional support in the technology-related demands of contemporary campus journalism.

Table 2. *Coaching Capability of School Paper Advisers*

Dimension	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Professional qualities	3.74	Effective	1
Coaching attitude	3.70	Effective	2
Communication skills	3.63	Effective	3
Analytical skills	3.51	Effective	4
Technological knowledge	3.24	Fairly Effective	5
Overall coaching capability	3.56	Effective	-

Note. Effective = 3.25-4.00; Fairly Effective = 2.50-3.24; Less Effective = 1.75-2.49; Not Effective = 1.00-1.74.

The high ratings for professional qualities and coaching attitude suggest that SPAs understood the ethical and developmental aspects of their role. The comparatively lower technological-knowledge mean is consistent with the changing media environment described in journalism education literature. Digital layout, online research, multimedia production, and responsible social media practices require continuous updating because the tools and platforms used in journalism continue to evolve (Du & Thornburg, 2011; Hewett, 2016).

Differences in Coaching Capability According to Profile

The analysis showed no significant differences in coaching capability according to age, gender, educational attainment, years of teaching experience, academic rank, or school location. Relevant trainings attended was the only profile variable associated with a significant difference in coaching capability ($F = 6.99, p = .001$). The finding reinforces the importance of structured professional development. While background characteristics did not distinguish coaching capability, exposure to relevant training appeared to strengthen advisers' readiness to perform their roles.

Table 3. *Differences in Coaching Capability According to Profile Variables*

Profile Variable	F Computed	p-value	Interpretation
Age	0.58	.630	Not Significant
Gender	2.54	.112	Not Significant
Educational attainment	0.75	.560	Not Significant
Years of teaching experience	2.38	.070	Not Significant
Academic rank	0.78	.540	Not Significant
Relevant trainings attended	6.99	.001	Significant
School location	0.574	.450	Not Significant

Note. Statistical significance was evaluated at the .05 level.

The significant training-related difference supports Rao's (2009) view that professional development can address capability gaps and provide teachers with necessary competencies. For Nueva Ecija SPAs, the priority is not to replace established coaching practices but to strengthen areas that are less developed, particularly technological knowledge.

Proposed Training and Development Plan

Based on the results, a focused training and development plan is proposed for secondary SPAs in the division. The plan prioritizes technological knowledge while reinforcing ethical coaching, communication, and analytical practice. It may be implemented through division-based sessions, school-based learning action cells, and follow-through technical assistance.

Table 4. *Proposed Training and Development Plan for School Paper Advisers*

Priority Area	Suggested Learning Focus	Expected Output
Digital layout and publication tools	Hands-on use of word-processing, desktop-publishing, and image-editing tools for school publications	Draft digital school-paper page or publication template
Online research and verification	Internet research, source evaluation, access to public information, and fact-checking practices	Verified source map and reporting checklist
Multimedia and social media journalism	Responsible social media use, multimedia storytelling, ethical online dissemination, and audience awareness	Short multimedia campus-journalism output
Data-informed reporting	Observation, data gathering, basic data interpretation, and evidence-based reporting	Data-supported campus news or feature article
Coaching clinic and mentoring	Peer feedback, coaching demonstrations, learning action cells, and quarterly technical assistance	Individual SPA development plan and coaching portfolio

Note. The proposed plan is based on the comparatively lower technological-knowledge rating and the significant difference associated with relevant training.

CONCLUSION

The secondary SPAs of Nueva Ecija demonstrated effective overall coaching capability. Their strongest areas were professional qualities, coaching attitude, communication skills, and analytical skills. Technological knowledge, although still present, remained the weakest dimension and was rated fairly effective. This indicates that the advisers have a sound professional foundation but need targeted assistance to respond more fully to the technological requirements of contemporary campus journalism.

Coaching capability did not differ significantly according to age, gender, educational attainment, years of teaching experience, academic rank, or school location. Relevant trainings attended was the only profile variable associated with a significant difference. The finding establishes a clear rationale for a sustained training and development plan that provides equitable opportunities for SPAs to strengthen digital and technical competencies while consolidating their existing coaching strengths.

Recommendations

The Schools Division of Nueva Ecija may implement a sustained training and development plan for SPAs, with priority given to technological knowledge, digital layout, online research, source verification, multimedia storytelling, and responsible social media use. Campus journalism may be included regularly in school-based and division-based learning sessions rather than offered only as an occasional activity.

School heads may support SPAs by providing appropriate time, resources, and opportunities for professional development. Schools may establish campus journalism clinics or learning action cells where advisers can share practices, mentor less experienced colleagues, and receive technical assistance. Teachers may also be encouraged to pursue graduate studies and relevant certifications that strengthen their professional growth.

Future studies may examine additional factors that influence journalism coaching capability and may use qualitative or mixed-method designs to explore the advisers' experiences in greater depth. Follow-up evaluation may also be conducted after the implementation of the proposed training plan to determine its effect on SPA competence and school publication performance.

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